

Determination of Zeta-potential of Quartz Particles in Dilute Solutions of KCl

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True zeta-potential of quartz particles of graded size in dilute KCl solutions has been measured by electro-osmotic and sedimentation potential methods. The values obtained by the former is 124 mv and that by latter, 133 mv, the agreement between the two being satisfactory; the mean value of ζ is taken as 129 mv.

Bull and Gortner (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1932, **36**, 111) by using the streaming potential method measured the zeta-potential of sintered quartz particles forming a diaphragm and found the magnitude of the potential to decrease with the decrease in size of the particles forming the diaphragm. Wood (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, **68**, 432) attributed this variation to the effect of the decrease in radius of the pores relative to the thickness of the double layer with decreasing particle size. The equation deduced by him is represented as

$$\eta \frac{HK}{P} = M - \frac{1}{2a} \sum_i d_i \Delta M_i \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

where H is the streaming potential at a pressure P ; M and d are the moment and the thickness of the double layer respectively and a is the radius of the pores of the diaphragm. Ghosh and co-workers (this *Journal*, 1953, **30**, 601) have, however, shown that the observations of Bull and Gortner can be accounted for quantitatively by an equation derived by taking the effect of surface conductance of the quartz particles into consideration. Their equation can be expressed as

$$\frac{1}{\zeta_a} = \frac{1}{\zeta} + \frac{m}{r} \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

where ζ and ζ_a are true and apparent zeta-potentials respectively, r , the radius of the particles, and m is a constant under the condition of the experiment and includes surface conductance.

In view of the facts mentioned above, an attempt has been made by the present author to determine the true zeta-potential of quartz particles of graded size in dilute solutions of KCl by two methods, namely, the electro-osmotic and the sedimentation potential methods.

EXPERIMENTAL

A quartz sample, previously ignited at 1000°, was broken into pieces and ground in an agate mortar and sieved to obtain particles of a definite size. The first three samples were prepared by standard sieves and the last one by sedimentation of a fine suspension

in water. Each sample was boiled with aqua regia, washed with conductivity water, and finally ignited in an electric furnace at 800°.

Electro-osmotic Experiment

Electro-osmotic measurements were carried out in the usual manner as described by Mukherjee (this *Journal*, 1927, 4, 461). A sample in sufficient amount was transferred to the same U-tube so that particles forming the diaphragm occupied a definite volume, care being taken that the sediment in the U-tube settled firmly in order to prevent its moving with the liquid. The particles in the diaphragm were washed by percolation with a solution of KCl of the desired concentration until conductance of the wash liquid was the same as that of the KCl solution used. Four such diaphragms, each with a particular sample, were made and electro-osmotic experiments were carried out with KCl solutions of the desired strength. From these data the values of apparent zeta-potential, ζ_a , were calculated using Smoluchowski's equation. A plot of $1/\zeta_a$ against $1/r$ gave a straight line. From the intercept of the straight line on $1/\zeta_a$ axis, the true zeta-potential, ζ , was found. The value of r used was the mean of that of the smallest and the largest of the particles in a given sample. The sieves were so selected that the difference in size between the smallest and the largest particles in a given sample was quite small. The results are recorded in Tables I and II.

TABLE I

Solution = 1×10^{-5} M-KCl. Sp. conduc. = 2.82×10^{-6} ohm $^{-1}$. Temp. = 30°.

Size range ($r \times 10^4$ cm).	(Mean) $1/r \times 10^{-1}$.	ζ_a .	$1/\zeta_a$.
124-152	7.25	80 mv	0.0125
89-105	10.30	60	0.0145
56-76	15.20	58	0.0172
41-49	22.20	47	0.0213

ζ found from intercept (vide Fig. 1) on $1/\zeta_a$ axis is 124 mv.

TABLE II

Solution = 3×10^{-5} M-KCl. Sp. conduc. = 6.1×10^{-6} ohm $^{-1}$. Temp. = 30°.

Size range ($r \times 10^4$ cm).	(Mean) $1/r \times 10^{-1}$.	ζ_a .	$1/\zeta_a$.
124-152	7.25	86.0 mv	0.0116
89-105	10.30	81.0	0.0123
56-76	15.20	74.5	0.0134
41-49	22.20	65.0	0.0154

ζ found from intercept (vide Fig. 1) on $1/\zeta_a$ axis is 104 mv.

Measurement of Sedimentation Potential

The sedimentation cell used was similar to that designed by Quist and Washburn (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 62, 3169). Doubly distilled water of about 1×10^{-6} ohm $^{-1}$ conduc-